

Effect of Gamification Principles and Perceived Ease of Use of Gamification in Mobile Devices on Customer Engagement and Flow State to Increase Mobile Shopping Loyalty of Shopee Marketplace Users

Juria Hastuti¹, Permana Honeyta², Syafruddin Chan³

^{1,2,3} MM Study Program, FEB Syiah Kuala University

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 14 October 2022	The purpose of this research is to analyze the role of Gamification Principles and Perceived Ease of Use of Gamification in Mobile Devices on Customer Engagement and Flow State to Increase Mobile Shopping Loyalty of Shopee Marketplace Users in Aceh Province. The population used in this study was the entire population in this study were all Shopee users in Aceh Province. The number of samples in this study was 200 people. The sampling technique used is non-probability convenience sampling. Data processing was carried out using SPSS and Amos software using the structural equation model (SEM) technique. The results showed that of the 7 direct influence hypotheses tested, there was one that was not significant, namely the Effect of Gamification Principles on Shopping_Loyalty. The highest coefficient of influence that determines customers to become loyal online buyers is Customer Engagement. This means that the higher the level of customer engagement due to the gamification of this shopee brand, the higher the level of customer loyalty to the Shopee marketplace.
Corresponding Author: Syafruddin Chan	
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1. INTRODUCTION

In Indonesia, this online shopping site is growing quite rapidly. Revenue in the eCommerce market is projected to reach US\$62.59 billion by 2022. Revenue is expected to show an annual growth rate (CAGR 2022-2025) of 12.95%, resulting in a projected market volume of US\$90.19 billion by 2025. With a projected volume market of US\$1,412.00bn in 2022, most of the revenue is generated in China. In the eCommerce market, the number of users is expected to reach 221.0 million users by 2025. User penetration will reach 64.1% by 2022 and is expected to reach 77.0% by 2025. The average revenue per user (ARPU) is estimated to reach US\$349.80. According to iPrice Insights, the competition for online shopping sites in Indonesia in 2020 has 41 online shopping sites and Shopee is one of them. To remain competitive, the loyalty factor must be a major concern. This is important to do because acquisitions require much higher costs than retaining existing customers (Wertz, 2018). In addition, increasing customer retention by 5% can increase company profits by 25% (Reichheld & Detrick, 2003). This shows how valuable a user's sense of loyalty is to marketplace organizers.

To increase a sense of user loyalty, customer engagement is one of the implementations of the paradigm that appears in the academic literature and practitioner discussions as a predictor of loyalty (So et al., 2016). In this regard, evidence from the previous literature was collected and examined to contribute in terms of customer engagement, and how customer engagement can contribute to the development of customer loyalty. In addition to engagement, flow state is also one of the things that can increase the loyalty of marketplace users. In a state of flow, a person is completely immersed in what he is doing. It is a state and feeling of synergistic focus, full involvement, and success in the process of an activity (Nakamura, 2009). One way that can be done to embrace a wider market and increase loyalty to its users is to add entertainment features to the application, such as applying the concept of gamification (Putri & Nugrahani, 2020). According to (Flicker, 2015) The emergence of the technological hype cycle in the marketing sector has made gamification increasingly have its place as one of the strategies to increase customer engagement. The concept of gamification is getting more and more attention recently from both academics and business practitioners.

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Taking advantage of the popularity of this gamification concept, shopee as an online shopping mall site is also starting to try to improve its product *customer engagement* through the use of this concept. Many games are included in the website so that the traffic that is entered into the shopee site is not only those who have and want to shop but also other segments who want to try the games on this site, such as Shopee Tanam, to play Shopee Tanam, players must plant seeds plant and water it every day. The player will get a prize if the planted fruit is successfully harvested. Interestingly, players can ask for water assistance from other Shopee users. The largest marketplace visitor in Indonesia in 2021, in the first position, is Tokopedia. The number of monthly visitors to the Tokopedia site reached 158.1 million visits. Shopee occupies the second position, this platform is visited by around 134.4 million. Bukalapak is also the marketplace with the most web visitors in 2021. Visitors to this platform reached 30.1 million visits in that period, followed by Lazada, Blibli, Orami., and Ralali (Siti Nur Aeni, 2022)

From the data above, the problem is that the Shopee marketplace is still under other marketplaces. Even if you look at the development of traffic coming into the Shopee website, it outperforms other e-marketplace websites. on customer loyalty in the Shopee online store(Alfi Layli Rohmatin, 2021)The question is how far the concept of gamification and perceived ease of use of gamification in mobile devices carried by Shopee can maintain customer engagement and flow state which has an impact on increasing mobile shopping loyalty from Shopee users? This is based on the facts that occur about the effectiveness of gamification in the context of changing one's behavior as conveyed by(Tobon et al., 2020). He stated that gamification applied to online consumer decisions requires a psychological theory approach to determine which elements and mechanisms work best in a game context to program these elements and design interactive, fun, and useful information systems. It is not enough to determine which elements function in the game context, especially those that meet technological requirements such as the perceived ease of use of gamification in mobile devices which are part of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) concept initiated by Venkatesh & Davis, (2000). Research related to the ease of technology and usefulness of technology in this online shopping environment has also been carried out by Ramayah & Ignatius, (2005).

In contrast to previous studies which discussed the concept of gamification in desktop-based online marketing, this study tries to discuss it from the perspective of mobile devices. In addition, the discussion of gamification is also integrated with customer engagement and flow state, which references are still rarely found in previous studies.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Gamification Principle

Previous research on gamification and customer engagement has been carried out several times(Rodrigues et al., 2016). The results of this study reveal that there is a positive influence between gamification and customer engagement. Law et al., (2014) have linked gamification as one of the technologies that will help increase customer satisfaction and engagement in the future. Several principles of gamification can drive customer engagement through expectations. This finding contradicts the widespread notion of designing effective gamified applications that "bind" customers by making them use gamified applications repeatedly and in unplanned ways.(Rodrigues et al., 2016). However, just checking a gamified app doesn't mean that customers are interacting with it or changing their behavior.(Kozak et al., 2010).

H1: Effect of Gamification Principles on Customer Engagement

H3: The Effect of Gamification Principle Variables on Shopping Loyalty Cars

2.2 Perceived Ease of Use Gamification in Mobile Device

Departing from the theory developed by(Venkatesh & Science, 2000)namely the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) it predicts individual acceptance of using technology or systems supported by perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. Shopee's online shopping services through service offerings and the features provided can provide benefits and convenience for its users. So this is felt to be able to make users accept the existence of Shopee's online shopping service by using the service. In the existing literature, it is rare to find studies in the context of mobile shopping that include the concept of flow in their research(Chen et al., 2020). Though flow has been widely used in research within the scope of information technology(Song & Liu, 2021)including research on online shopping(Chen et al., 2020). And in the research that has been done(Chiu et al., 2014)revealed that flow can provide deeper insight into consumers. The concept of flow is described as a person's psychological experience which is in an optimal state, which makes a person fully focused on his activities(Nakamura, 2009). Liu et al., (2013) state that there is a positive influence between perceived ease of use on loyalty. Temporary(Tobon et al., 2020)states that ease of use is a person's belief that using a particular system is easy (free effort). In carrying out its use, consumers need information about online transportation.

H2: Effect of Perceived Ease of Use in Mobile Device Variables on Flow State

H4: The Influence of the Perceived Ease of Use of gamification in Mobile Device Variables on Customer Loyalty Variables

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2.3 Customer Engagement

Customer engagement marketing—defined as a company's deliberate effort to motivate, empower, and measure the customer's contribution to the marketing function—marks a change in marketing research and business practices (Verhoef et al., 2010). After defining and differentiating engagement marketing, (Jaakkola & Alexander, 2014), presenting typologies of its two main forms and offering principles linking certain strategic elements to customer outcomes and thus firm performance, theorize that engagement marketing effectiveness arises from the formation of psychological ownership and trust. self. transformation. (Grégoire et al., 2018) provide evidence to support the principles derived through case illustrations, as well as a quasi-experimental field test of the main principles of this customer engagement concept, as well as linking it with customer loyalty.

H5: The Influence of Customer Engagement Variables on Customer Loyalty

2.4 Flow State

According to positive psychologist Mihály Csíkszentmihályi, what you are experiencing at that moment is known as a flow state, which is defined as "a state of optimal awareness in which we feel our best and do our best." Csíkszentmihályi, who popularized the term in his 1990 book, flow mental state

2.5 Research Model

The model in this study is shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Research Framework

3. RESEARCH METHOD

The population used in this study was the entire population in this study were all Shopee users in Aceh Province. The number of samples in this study was 200 people, which was obtained by multiplying 20 indicators by the number 10. (Hair et al., 2006). The sampling technique used is non-probability convenience sampling. Data processing was carried out using

involves “being fully engaged in an activity for its own sake. The ego falls away. Time flies. Every action, movement, and thought must follow from the previous one, like playing jazz. In our whole existence, we are involved, and we use our skills to the fullest. Factors that can accompany this flow state are having a clear goal of what you want to achieve, concentration and focus, participating in intrinsically rewarding activities, loss of feelings of self-awareness, immortality; losing track of the elapsed time, being able to quickly assess own progress; instant feedback on performance, lack of awareness of physical needs, full focus on the activity itself (Bilgihan, Kandampully, and Zhang 2016).

H6: Effect of Flow State Variables on Customer Loyalty

2.5 Mobile Shopping Loyalty

Loyalty marketing is a marketing strategy that focuses on retaining existing customers by offering rewards in the form of discounts, exclusive access, free products, and more. (Grégoire et al., 2018). The importance of customer loyalty impacts almost every metric that is critical to running a business. Without happy customers who keep buying from you, your business will not survive. New customers (as we'll talk about below) tend to be more expensive to acquire and don't cost as much as repeat loyal customers.

SPSS and Amos software using the structural equation model (SEM) technique.

The measurement of the Gamification Principles variable uses 5 measurement scales developed by (Rodrigues et al., 2016). For the Perceived Ease of Use Gamification in Mobile Device variable using 4 measurement scales from (Davis, 1985). Then for Customer Engagement, 4

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indicators are used which were adopted:(Grégoire et al., 2018). Flow state using 4 measuring tools developed by(Nakamura, 2009). For Mobile Shopping Loyalty using 4 measuring tools adapted from Robby (2017). Testing the causality hypothesis was carried out using a structural equation model with criteria CR > 1.960 and P < 0.05

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

4.1 Characteristics of Respondents

The characteristics of respondents in this study are mostly men with age levels between 30 to 36 years and are married and have a high school and bachelor's education. The type of

occupation of the respondents is mostly private employees, then self-employed. Meanwhile, civil servants are only 3.00 % of the total number of respondents.

4.2 Research Instrument Tests

a. Validity test

A validity test is conducted to measure how valid each indicator is in representing each variable. If it turns out that there are indicators that are not valid, they will be eliminated and only valid indicators will be maintained. Validity testing was carried out using construct validity techniques.

Table 1. Constructive Validity Results

	Estimate	SE	CR	P
a25 <--- Perc_ofUsed	1,000			
a26 <--- Perc_ofUsed	1.067	,083	12,863	***
a27 <--- Perc_ofUsed	,979	,085	11.565	***
a28 <--- Perc_ofUsed	1,129	,091	12,341	***
a29 <--- Gami_Principle	1,000			
a30 <--- Gami_Principle	1,179	,160	7,368	***
a31 <--- Gami_Principle	1,241	,167	7,446	***
a32 <--- Gami_Principle	1,262	,165	7,644	***
a33 <--- FlowState	1,000			
a35 <--- FlowState	,846	,107	7,876	***
a1 <--- FlowState	,872	,118	7,379	***
a16 <--- Cust_Engagemant	1,000			
a15 <--- Cust_Engagemant	1.181	,165	7,155	***
a14 <--- Cust_Engagemant	1.484	,198	7.505	***
a13 <--- Cust_Engagemant	1.550	,206	7.512	***
a17 <--- Shopping_Loyalty	1,000			
a18 <--- Shopping_Loyalty	,813	,107	7.573	***
a19 <--- Shopping_Loyalty	1,110	,114	9.739	***
a20 <--- Shopping_Loyalty	,784	,108	7,251	***

From the results of the validity testing that has been carried out, it turns out that all existing indicators meet the requirements, namely the P value is less than 0.05. Thus, all the indicators involved in this study deserve to be maintained.

4.3 Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

CFA is part of Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis. SEM is a complete model analysis intended to test the models

and hypotheses developed in this study. This analysis was carried out after analyzing the measurement model through the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) test. From the results of the CFA test, it is known that there is one indicator in the variable of job competence, namely the X2.4 indicator which has a loading factor value of 0.5 so the indicator is not included in the next test. SEM analysis was carried out by testing the significance of causality through the regression cohesion test.

Table 2. Confirmatory Factor Analysis

	Estimate
a25 <--- Perc_ofUsed	,785
a26 <--- Perc_ofUsed	,840
a27 <--- Perc_ofUsed	,771
a28 <--- Perc_ofUsed	,812
a29 <--- Gami_Principle	,526

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			Estimate
a30	<---	Gami_Principle	,786
a31	<---	Gami_Principle	,798
a32	<---	Gami_Principle	,848
a33	<---	FlowState	,722
a34	<---	FlowState	,444
a35	<---	FlowState	,651
a1	<---	FlowState	,582
a16	<---	Cust_Engagemant	,543
a15	<---	Cust_Engagemant	,710
a14	<---	Cust_Engagemant	,779
a13	<---	Cust_Engagemant	,781
a17	<---	Shopping_Loyalty	,725
a18	<---	Shopping_Loyalty	,569
a19	<---	Shopping_Loyalty	,733
a20	<---	Shopping_Loyalty	,545

From the table above, it can be seen that there is 1 indicator that does not meet the requirements because it has a loading factor number below the required one, namely 0.5. So indicators a34 and this must be eliminated.

4.4 Goodness of Fit

Based on the results of the SEM analysis, it is known that the goodness of fit index value is still problematic. For GFI,

RMSEA TLI, and IFI, have exceeded their respective limit values. However, CMIN/DF and AGFI still do not meet the criteria. Therefore, model verification is still needed. After resizing the model by adding a covariance line to the items that have the largest MI value, the results met expectations. The goodness of fit value can be seen in Table 1 and the results of the structural equation modeling analysis can be seen in the following table.

Table 3. Evaluation of Criteria for Goodness of Fit Indices

No	<i>The goodness of Fit Indices</i>	Cut Off Value	Test results	Information
1	CMIN/DF	<2	1,931	Fit
2	RMSEA	0.08	0.068	Fit
3	GFI	0.90	0.884	Marginal Fit
4	AGFI	0.90	0.838	Marginal Fit
5	TLI	0.95	0.923	Fit
6.	IFI	0.96	0.940	Fit

All indicators tested for the feasibility of the model have exceeded the required threshold value so that the model can

be said to be fit and can be continued in the next data processing.

4.5 Hypotheses Testing with Structural Model

Table 4. Results of Structural Equation Modeling Analysis

Dependent		Independent	Estimate	SE	CR	P	Beta
FlowState	<---	Perc of Used	,514	,067	7,617	***	,844
Cust_Engagemant	<---	Gami Principle	,500	,092	5,443	***	,808
Shopping_Loyalty	<---	Perc ofUsed	,244	,108	2,259	,003	,269
Shopping_Loyalty	<---	Gami Principle	,003	,261	0.012	,991	,003
Shopping_Loyalty	<---	FlowState	,514	,067	7,617	***	,346
Shopping_Loyalty	<---	Cust Engagement	,675	,221	3.053	,002	,430

4.6 Direct Hypothesis Testing

Testing the Effect of Gamification Principles on customer engagement shows a CR value of 5,443 and a

probability of ***. So the effect of gamification principles on customer engagement is significant. The magnitude of the coefficient of the influence of gamification principles on

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customer engagement is 0.884, so the impact of the influence of gamification principles on customer engagement is significant at 88.4%. Testing the Effect of Gamification principles on flow state. shows the CR value of 0.813 and with a probability of 0.416so so the effect of brand image on customer satisfaction is not significant. The magnitude of the influence of brand image on customer satisfaction is also relatively small, only 0.120 or 12.0%. Testing the Effect of Product Availability on Repurchase Intention shows

a CR value of 11,450 and a probability of ***.so that it can be stated that the effect of product availability on repurchase intention is significant. The magnitude of the coefficient of the Effect of Product Availability on Repurchase Intention is 0.353 or 35.3%. Testing the Effect of Brand Image on Repurchase Intention shows a CR value of 5,727 and a probability of ***. The two values obtained do not meet the requirements for the acceptance of Ha, which is greater than 1.96 and the probability is less than 0.05.

Figure 2. Structural Model

4.7 Indirect Hypothesis Testing

Effect of Perceived ease of use gamification in a mobile device on mobile shopping loyalty through flow state.

	Gami Principle	Perc ofUsed	Gami Principle	Perc ofUsed
Cust_Engemant	-	-	-	-
FlowState	-	-	-	-
Shopping_Loyalty	,005	,001	0.347	0.292

Test results The effect of gamification principles on mobile shopping loyalty through customer engagement. has a p-value score of 0.005. Thus, it can be stated that the influence of gamification principles affects mobile shopping loyalty through customer engagement. The magnitude of the coefficient of the influence of gamification principles affects mobile shopping loyalty through customer engagement. is 0.0347 or 34.7%.

- a. Effect of Perceived ease of use gamification in a mobile device on mobile shopping loyalty through flow state.

The result of testing the effect of Perceived ease of use gamification in mobile devices on mobile shopping loyalty through flow state has a p-value score of 0.001. Thus it can be stated that the effect of Perceived ease-of-use gamification in mobile devices on mobile shopping loyalty through this flow state is significant. The magnitude of the coefficient of the effect of Perceived ease of use gamification in mobile devices on mobile shopping loyalty through flow state. is 0.292 or 29.2% .

4.9 Managerial Implications

If it is seen which variable has the greatest dominance in moving customers to repurchase, then customer engagement turns out to have the highest coefficient of influence compared to other variables. When viewed more closely from the measurement items variable, the statement I am always willing to try new features from the Shopee application is very common. Thus, the addition of new features, including the inclusion of the latest and varied online games, becomes the impetus to make customers return to the Shopee website. The increasing amount of traffic due to this new feature makes the job of a marketing manager to convert incoming traffic to the shopee web easier. One of the most difficult tasks is to drive traffic into the traffic funnel, which does require incentives. Gamification is one of the factors that encourage customers to always visit shopee and shopee can install interesting pop-up ads in the game that encourage customers to click on the attached link.

Meanwhile, for indirect effects, the two hypotheses are the effect of Perceived ease of use gamification in mobile devices on mobile shopping loyalty through flow state and the effect of gamification principles on mobile shopping loyalty through customer engagement. shows a significant effect. The coefficient of the effect of perceived ease of use gamification in mobile devices on mobile shopping loyalty through flow state is 0.347 or 34.7% while the coefficient of influence of gamification principles affects mobile shopping loyalty through customer engagement. Is 0.292 or 29.2%. When viewed from the magnitude value, we say that the influence generated by customer engagement in mediating the exogenous effect on the endogenous one is greater than the flow state.

5. CONCLUSION

Because my statement is always willing to try new features of the Shopee application, is a very common statement. Thus, the addition of new features, including the inclusion of the latest and varied online games, becomes the impetus to make customers return to the Shopee website. The increasing amount of traffic due to this new feature makes the job of a marketing manager to convert incoming traffic to the shopee web easier. One of the most difficult tasks is to drive traffic into the traffic funnel, which does require incentives.

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